

Heme-based gas-sensing riboceptors

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Abstract

Understanding how cells sense gases is a fundamental question in biology and is pivotal for the evolution of molecular and organismal life. In numerous organisms, gases can diffuse into, be transported, and even be generated. Controlling gases in the cellular environment is essential to prevent cellular and molecular damage due to uncontrolled interactions with gas derivatives. Consequently, the mechanisms governing acute gas sensing in various microorganisms have been experimentally elucidated. However, the scientific literature on gas sensing is largely based on protein-based gas receptors. As RNA-based G-quadruplex (G4) structures can also bind to heme, I propose that some of the heme-binding RNA G4 (acting alone or in combination with another ribozyme) are merely gas-sensing riboceptors.

Gases are among the evolutionarily oldest molecules, likely preceding the RNA world and potentially contributing to the formation of complex polymeric structures.¹⁻⁶ As RNA-based organisms evolved, gas sensing must have been one of the earliest mechanisms to develop. In my opinion, RNA-based gas-sensing riboreceptors must have played a pivotal role not only in organism evolution but also in the evolution of molecular machinery. Currently, protein-based gas-sensing gasoreceptors have been described in numerous organisms, from bacteria to humans.^{7,8} Even the RNA-binding protein DGCR8 (DiGeorge Critical Region 8), a pri-miRNA (primary miRNA) processing factor, serves as a heme-based NO/CO gasoreceptor with pri-miRNA processing activity.⁹⁻¹³ However, to the best of my knowledge, there is no scientific literature on RNA-based gas-sensing mechanisms (ribozyme, riboswitch, RNA-based gas sensor, receptor or riboreceptors, etc.). Does this mean it is yet to be experimentally demonstrated, or it has not been described in the literature with a unifying term similar to the parable of the blind men and the elephant?^{14,15} In my opinion, RNA-based G4 (G-quadruplex) structures that can regulate gene expression or mRNA stability by binding to heme are simply gas-sensing riboreceptors.¹⁶⁻¹⁹ Such RNA G4 structures have been described not only in mRNA but also in small and long ncRNAs (non-coding RNAs).^{20,21} RNA G4 has been shown to exhibit ribozyme activity and catalyze oxygen transfer reactions, acting as peroxidases and/or peroxygenases both *in vitro* and *in vivo*.^{17,18,22,23} Such RNA G4 structures with enzymatic activity have also been demonstrated in the C9orf72 (chromosome 9 open reading frame 72) gene, a gene implicated in neurodegenerative diseases such as ALS (Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis).²⁴⁻²⁶ However, the question arises whether heme can also be bound by gases (solute) *in vivo* under physiological conditions. If heme in soluble guanylate cyclase, a NO-sensing gasoreceptor, can be bound and activated via gas such as NO (nitric oxide), why not the heme in RNA G4 structures?²⁷ Overall, in my opinion, RNA G4 structures (either *per se* or associated with an additional signaling moiety or ribozyme), in addition to their role as heme scavengers or heme-based ribozymes, may also have a parallel role as gas-sensing riboreceptors.^{28,29}

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Savani Anbalagan: conceptualization, writing of the original draft, and review and editing.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

DISCLOSURE

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REFERENCES

1. Gesteland RF, Cech T, Atkins JF. *The RNA World: The Nature of Modern RNA Suggests a Prebiotic RNA World*. CSHL Press; 2006.
2. Higgs PG, Lehman N. The RNA World: molecular cooperation at the origins of life. *Nat Rev Genet* 2015; 16:7–17.
3. Saito H. The RNA world “hypothesis.” *Nat Rev Mol Cell Biol* 2022; 23:582.
4. Lazcano A, Miller SL. The Origin and Early Evolution of Life: Prebiotic Chemistry, the Pre-RNA World, and Time. *Cell* 1996; 85:793–8.
5. Pearce BKD, Pudritz RE, Semenov DA, Henning TK. Origin of the RNA world: The fate of nucleobases in warm little ponds. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2017; 114:11327–32.
6. Morasch M, Liu J, Dirscherl CF, Ianeselli A, Kühnlein A, Le Vay K, Schwintek P, Islam S, Corpinot MK, Scheu B, et al. Heated gas bubbles enrich, crystallize, dry, phosphorylate and encapsulate prebiotic molecules. *Nat Chem* 2019; 11:779–88.
7. Anbalagan S. Heme-based oxygen gasoreceptors. *Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab* 2024; 326:E178–81.
8. Anbalagan S. Oxygen is an essential gasotransmitter directly sensed via protein gasoreceptors. *Animal Model Exp Med* 2024;
9. Barr I, Smith AT, Chen Y, Senturia R, Burstyn JN, Guo F. Ferric, not ferrous, heme activates RNA-binding protein DGCR8 for primary microRNA processing. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 2012; 109:1919–24.
10. Faller M, Matsunaga M, Yin S, Loo JA, Guo F. Heme is involved in microRNA processing. *Nat Struct Mol Biol* 2007; 14:23–9.
11. Hines JP, Smith AT, Jacob JP, Lukat-Rodgers GS, Barr I, Rodgers KR, Guo F, Burstyn JN. CO and NO bind to Fe(II) DiGeorge critical region 8 heme but do not restore primary microRNA processing activity. *J Biol Inorg Chem* 2016; 21:1021–35.
12. Partin AC, Ngo TD, Herrell E, Jeong B-C, Hon G, Nam Y. Heme enables proper positioning of Drosha and DGCR8 on primary microRNAs. *Nat Commun* 2017; 8:1737.
13. Weitz SH, Gong M, Barr I, Weiss S, Guo F. Processing of microRNA primary transcripts requires heme in mammalian cells. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 2014; 111:1861–6.
14. Anbalagan S. “Blind men and an elephant”, the need for animals in research, drug safety studies, and understanding civilizational diseases. *Animal Model Exp Med* 2023; 6:627–33.
15. *The Blind Men and the Elephant*. Scholastic Incorporated; 1992.
16. Kharel P, Fay M, Manasova EV, Anderson PJ, Kurkin AV, Guo JU, Ivanov P. Stress promotes RNA G-quadruplex folding in human cells. *Nat Commun* 2023; 14:205.

17. Sen D, Poon LCH. RNA and DNA complexes with heme [Fe(III) heme] are efficient peroxidases and peroxygenases: how do they do it and what does it mean? *Crit Rev Biochem Mol Biol* 2011; 46:478–92.
18. Poon LC-H, Methot SP, Morabi-Pazooki W, Pio F, Bennet AJ, Sen D. Guanine-rich RNAs and DNAs that bind heme robustly catalyze oxygen transfer reactions. *J Am Chem Soc* 2011; 133:1877–84.
19. Shao X, Zhang W, Umar MI, Wong HY, Seng Z, Xie Y, Zhang Y, Yang L, Kwok CK, Deng X. RNA G-Quadruplex Structures Mediate Gene Regulation in Bacteria. *mBio* 2020; 11:e02926-19.
20. Figueiredo J, Santos T, Miranda A, Alexandre D, Teixeira B, Simões P, Lopes-Nunes J, Cruz C. Ligands as Stabilizers of G-Quadruplexes in Non-Coding RNAs. *Molecules* 2021; 26:6164.
21. Mou X, Liew SW, Kwok CK. Identification and targeting of G-quadruplex structures in MALAT1 long non-coding RNA. *Nucleic Acids Res* 2022; 50:397–410.
22. Grigg JC, Shumayrikh N, Sen D. G-quadruplex structures formed by expanded hexanucleotide repeat RNA and DNA from the neurodegenerative disease-linked C9orf72 gene efficiently sequester and activate heme. *PLoS One* 2014; 9:e106449.
23. Lat PK, Liu K, Kumar DN, Wong KKL, Verheyen EM, Sen D. High specificity and tight spatial restriction of self-biotinylation by DNA and RNA G-Quadruplexes complexed in vitro and in vivo with Heme. *Nucleic Acids Res* 2020; 48:5254–67.
24. Reddy K, Zamiri B, Stanley SYR, Macgregor RB, Pearson CE. The disease-associated r(GGGGCC)_n repeat from the C9orf72 gene forms tract length-dependent uni- and multimolecular RNA G-quadruplex structures. *J Biol Chem* 2013; 288:9860–6.
25. Fratta P, Mizielinska S, Nicoll AJ, Zloh M, Fisher EMC, Parkinson G, Isaacs AM. C9orf72 hexanucleotide repeat associated with amyotrophic lateral sclerosis and frontotemporal dementia forms RNA G-quadruplexes. *Sci Rep* 2012; 2:1016.
26. Geng Y, Cai Q. Role of C9orf72 hexanucleotide repeat expansions in ALS/FTD pathogenesis. *Front Mol Neurosci* 2024; 17:1322720.
27. Horst BG, Yokom AL, Rosenberg DJ, Morris KL, Hammel M, Hurley JH, Marletta MA. Allosteric activation of the nitric oxide receptor soluble guanylate cyclase mapped by cryo-electron microscopy. *Elife* 2019; 8:e50634.
28. Gray LT, Puig Lombardi E, Verga D, Nicolas A, Teulade-Fichou M-P, Londoño-Vallejo A, Maizels N. G-quadruplexes Sequester Free Heme in Living Cells. *Cell Chem Biol* 2019; 26:1681-1691.e5.
29. Mestre-Fos S, Ito C, Moore CM, Reddi AR, Williams LD. Human ribosomal G-quadruplexes regulate heme bioavailability. *J Biol Chem* 2020; 295:14855–65.